

Analyzing Temporal Changes in the Danube Delta: A Time Series Study with Co-registered Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 Data

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Abstract—Significant environmental changes have affected the Danube Delta, necessitating advanced monitoring methods that integrate satellite imagery and precise algorithms. This study offers a comprehensive time series analysis of temporal changes in the Danube Delta using co-registered synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and multispectral (MS) satellite data. Our primary objective is to monitor both seasonal and long-term changes. We developed a machine learning (ML) algorithm utilizing time series co-registered Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) data, employing a combination of supervised and unsupervised techniques, including Support Vector Machines (SVM), t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), and K-means clustering. Our results indicate that the ensemble technique of t-SNE and SVM enhances accuracy to nearly 97.28%. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) analysis reveals significant fluctuations in vegetation health throughout the year, with high values in February and November, and lower values during April and the summer months. This approach effectively supports comprehensive environmental monitoring, helps protect the Danube Delta, and promotes sustainable management.

Index Terms—Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), Multispectral (MS), Machine Learning (ML), time series analysis, co-registered Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) data, Support Vector Machines (SVM), t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), K-means clustering, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

I. INTRODUCTION

The Danube Delta, one of Europe’s most important natural areas, is undergoing rapid and major environmental change [1]. The biodiversity and ecological balance of the area are seriously threatened by these changes, making sophisticated monitoring techniques necessary to adequately track and manage these dynamics. Current monitoring approaches frequently underestimate the temporal and spatial complexity of these changes [2].

The combination of synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and multispectral (MS) satellite imaging provides significant tools for environmental monitoring in Remote sensing (RS) technology. However, to fully utilize these tools, the enormous amounts of data created must be analyzed using precise and complex algorithms. RS and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies have revolutionized environmental management and

monitoring. AI improves the processing and interpretation of the useful data on Earth’s surface that RS offers [3] [4].

Despite advancements in AI and RS, existing methods for monitoring temporal changes in the Danube Delta are often insufficient, relying on single-sensor data or conventional analytical procedures [5]. This limitation underscores the need for innovative methods that provide more precise and timely information on seasonal and long-term changes. Addressing this gap is crucial for the effective conservation and sustainable management of the Danube Delta, influencing policy decisions and conservation efforts [6] [7].

Previous studies have used similar satellite imagery to monitor changes such as floods, employing compression metrics and active learning for feature extraction, with confirmed accuracy [8]. Additionally, the use of multiple RS methods has successfully identified different macrophytes with high precision [9]. These studies demonstrate the potential of advanced RS and Machine Learning (ML) techniques in environmental monitoring, providing a foundation for the approach taken in this research.

The primary objective of this study is to develop and apply a comprehensive ML framework to monitor temporal changes in the Danube Delta. This framework uses time series analysis of coregistered Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite data to analyze both seasonal variations and long-term trends. The present study analyzes ecological shifts in the Danube Delta through S1 and S2 imagery, focusing on vegetation and water coverage. We enhance change detection accuracy by integrating ML with visual analysis, emphasizing the role of RS in conservation and ecosystem management. In particular, the research aims to improve change detection accuracy and develop ML models using both supervised and unsupervised learning methods. It also aims to study the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) to identify seasonal patterns and notable variations, and to assess the effectiveness of different ML algorithms in enhancing environmental monitoring and management strategies.

The current research incorporates a combination of supervised and unsupervised ML approaches, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor

Embedding (t-SNE), and K-means clustering. These algorithms are used to detect and classify temporal changes in time series data from coregistered S1 and S2 images. The integration of SAR and MS data, along with advanced ML methods, represents a novel approach to capture the Danube Delta's complex temporal changes [10] [11].

The objectives of this research include the temporal analysis of changes in land use and cover throughout the Danube Delta, with an emphasis on both short- and long-term changes. The resolution, availability, and computational resources needed for prolonged model training and validation impose limitations on the process of model training and validation, even though high accuracy is the desired result.

The subsequent part of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the suggested methodology, which includes data preprocessing and ML techniques. Section III contains the experimental findings and remarks. Section IV concludes the paper with major findings and recommendations for future research.

II. METHODOLOGY

Our approach enhances the accuracy of satellite images by correcting distortions and co-registering S1 and S2 images. This preprocessing step ensures that data from different sensors align perfectly for subsequent analysis. We utilize a Gabor filter for detailed analysis and apply t-SNE for dimensionality reduction, followed by K-means clustering to verify the number of classes and perform classification. SVM classification further differentiates changes in water, land, and vegetation, significantly enhancing change detection precision. The methodology is divided into main parts: Data Collection, Data Preprocessing and Co-Registration, Patch Extraction and Gabor Feature Representation, Clustering and Classification, and Time Series Analysis and NDVI. [12].

A. Data Collection

Data were collected from the Copernicus Open Access Hub (SciHub) for ten different months during 2021 and 2022. Efforts were made to select images with minimal cloud cover, using S1 and S2 images taken on the same day and hour whenever possible. Specific dates for the S1 and S2 data collection are shown in Table I.

The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) data file was obtained from an external elevation data website (<https://srtm.csi.cgiar.org>) and used in SNAP. However, this external SRTM file included a default mask, causing certain parts of the dataset to be converted to NaN (Not a Number). This complication added to the preprocessing challenges. To address this, the masks used for classification were designed to exclude the NaN regions.

Date per data											
S/D	Feb	Apr	Jun	Jul	Aug	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	
S1	28	22	28	28	15	31	01	19	24	16	
S2	26	22	26	31	15	29	03	23	22	16	

TABLE I: The date of per ten S1 and S2 data in 2021-2022.

B. Data Preprocessing and Co-Registration

We start by preprocessing the satellite images to correct any geometric distortions by co-registering the S1 data with the S2 data. This step is crucial to ensure that each pixel represents the same geographic location across all datasets, facilitating accurate temporal analysis. The preprocessing of S1 data involves several steps using SNAP software.

C. Patch Extraction and Gabor Feature Representation

We propose extracting patches from the scene image using a regular grid of 60x60 pixels. A Gabor filter is then applied to these patches with $K = 4$ orientations, $S = 6$ scales, using a window size of 39x39 pixels, resulting in 48-dimensional feature vectors [13].

The Gabor wavelet transform of a co-registered image $I(x, y)$ is defined as:

$$W_{mn}(x, y) = \int I(x_1, y_1) * g_{mn}(x - x_1, y - y_1) dx_1 dy_1$$

where $g_{mn}(x, y)$ is the mother Gabor wavelet, $m = 0, 1, \dots, K - 1$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, S - 1$, and $*$ represents the complex conjugate. The mean μ_{mn} and standard deviation σ_{mn} of the transform coefficients' magnitudes are used for classification and retrieval:

$$\mu_{mn} = \int \int |W_{mn}(x, y)| dx dy$$

$$\sigma_{mn} = \sqrt{\int \int (W_{mn}(x, y) - \mu_{mn})^2 dx dy}$$

These feature components, along with the orientations and scales, generate a feature vector:

$$\bar{f} = [\mu_{00}\sigma_{00}\mu_{01} \dots \mu_{35}\sigma_{35}]$$

D. Clustering and Classification

Our work is divided into two stages: unsupervised and supervised classification. First, the extracted features \bar{f} are used for unsupervised classification through k-means clustering, with a maximum of three classes to identify distinct temporal patterns.

For supervised classification, we employ a multi-class SVM classifier to distinguish between water bodies, land, and vegetation. To assess the importance of the number of feature vector dimensions, we use t-SNE, an algorithm well-suited for feature reduction on non-linear data [14].

E. Time Series Analysis and NDVI

We extended the analysis to a time series spanning ten different dates, creating and analyzing multiplied masks to capture comprehensive temporal changes. NDVI was analyzed to identify significant changes and seasonal patterns.

Fig. 1: A collection of RGB image, mask, feature maps, and additional land, vegetation, and waterbody images over various months from February 2021 to February 2022.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We conducted a time series analysis using S1 and S2 imagery collected over 10 months from 2021 to 2022. The preprocessing phase ensured data consistency and precise alignment of multi-temporal images, enhancing the validity of our analyses.

We employed both unsupervised and supervised techniques, including t-SNE and K-means clustering, along with SVM for scene classification. Additionally, we calculated the NDVI to monitor vegetation dynamics. The primary objectives were to determine which bands from S1 and S2 were most suitable for our analysis when applying t-SNE and K-means clustering, and to decide on the optimal number of classes. We used SVM for the classification of the scene to see if it performed better alone or in combination with t-SNE. Furthermore, comparing the NDVI analysis with the classification results helped validate the accuracy of our findings. Consequently, the results are organized into two main sections: Clustering and Classification Results, and NDVI Analysis.

A. Clustering and Classification Results

t-SNE visualized high-dimensional data in a lower-dimensional space, highlighting distinct clusters of land cover types. K-means clustering identified three optimal clusters: water bodies, vegetation, and land. Using t-SNE and K-means can help us to determine which bands to work on, the Vertical Vertical (VV) band is the best choice compared to others. The combination of t-SNE and K-means clustering provided a comprehensive view of the Danube Delta's land cover dynamics.

The SVM classification was applied to the Danube Delta time series data using t-SNE, focusing on three classes: land, vegetation, and water bodies. The classification results for ten different dates are presented in Fig. 1. The feature maps for each date demonstrate the spatial distribution of the three land cover types across the Danube Delta, clearly

delineating areas dominated by land, vegetation, and water bodies. Consistent patterns observed across different months indicate stable classification performance and the ability to accurately distinguish between these land cover types. In February 2021 (Fig. 1c), clear distinctions between water bodies, vegetation, and land areas are evident. By April 2021 (Fig. 1d), distinct clusters of the three classes are still present, with some seasonal variations. June 2021 (Fig. 1e) shows increased vegetation cover corresponding to the growing season, which peaks in July (Fig. 1f) and August 2021 (Fig. 1g) with substantial green areas. Post-harvest changes are visible in October 2021 (Fig. 1h), with some areas returning to land or water body classifications. From November 2021 (Fig. 1i) to February 2022 (Fig. 1l), the maps indicate a transition back to the non-growing season, with increased land and water body areas and reduced vegetation.

The monthly classification accuracy for each date, presented in Fig. 2, shows that the SVM classifier maintained high accuracy across all dates, indicating robust performance in differentiating between land, vegetation, and water bodies. The accuracies were as follows: February 2021 (95.32%), April 2021 (94.62%), June 2021 (92.93%), July 2021 (87.31%), August 2021 (94.32%), October 2021 (83.75%), November 2021 (97.28%), December 2021 (88.95%), January 2022 (94.50%), and February 2022 (96.20%). The classifier exhibited the highest accuracy in November 2021 (97.28%) and the lowest in October 2021 (83.75%). These variations can be attributed to seasonal changes affecting the spectral characteristics of the land cover types. Overall, the SVM classification demonstrated reliable and consistent performance in mapping the Danube Delta's land cover dynamics over the studied period.

B. NDVI Analysis

The graph of Monthly NDVI Averages in Fig. 3 for the Danube Delta shows significant fluctuations in vegetation health and density throughout the year. In February 2021,

Fig. 2: Classification Accuracy

Fig. 3: NDVI Averages

the NDVI is high at approximately 0.8, indicating healthy vegetation, but it sharply declines to around 0.55 in April 2021. This low level persists through June, July, and August 2021, suggesting minimal vegetation growth during these months. A notable increase occurs in October 2021, with the NDVI peaking at around 0.85 and remaining high at 0.88 in November 2021, reflecting a period of robust vegetation health. However, the NDVI drops again to about 0.58 in December 2021, then rises sharply to approximately 0.83 in January 2022, before declining once more to around 0.55 in February 2022. These NDVI trends highlight the seasonal variations and potential environmental impacts on the vegetation dynamics in the Danube Delta.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our research combines SAR and MS imagery with ML to accurately monitor ecological changes in the Danube Delta. By using advanced processing techniques, we've significantly improved the detection of changes in land, water, and vegetation, offering a valuable approach to ecological conservation. Using t-SNE and K-means helps us determine the number of classes and the suitable VV band for further analyses. Applying SVM to t-SNE data leads to higher accuracy. The combined results of SVM classification and NDVI analysis reveal significant seasonal variations and trends in the Danube Delta region. Both methods highlight the dynamic nature of land cover and vegetation health throughout the year. The key findings are:

- **Seasonal Variations:** Both SVM classification and NDVI analysis show distinct seasonal patterns, with robust vegetation health in early spring and late fall, and reduced vegetation during summer months.
- **Classification Accuracy:** The SVM classifier consistently distinguished between land, vegetation, and water bodies with high accuracy, reflecting stable classification performance despite seasonal changes.
- **Vegetation Health:** NDVI analysis corroborated classification results, showing high NDVI values during peak

vegetation periods and significant drops during non-growing seasons.

These analyses indicate significant seasonal changes in the Danube Delta, underscoring the importance of monitoring and understanding these dynamics for effective environmental management and conservation efforts. Future research should focus on integrating additional data sources and refining ML models to further enhance monitoring capabilities.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860370.

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